

**Integration of Hydrological Simulations into the Design Process to
Assess the Performance of Green Infrastructure Designs**

A Case Study of the City of LaPlace, LA

Master's Thesis

Clara Jimenez

Spring 2025

Mentor: Brendan Harmon

Robert Reich School of Landscape Architecture

Louisiana State University

Abstract

With the growing threat of flooding in coastal and inland communities, it is necessary to migrate nature-based solutions such as green infrastructure. However, one of the challenges that designers face with this strategy lies in the design phase where it is difficult to quantify the performance with traditional design tools. Thus, there is an incentive to incorporate hydrological models within GIS to aid designers in quantifying performance. The **goal** of this research is to demonstrate **that hydrological simulations can be used as a design tool for designers—such as landscape architects & architects— to analyze the feasibility of green infrastructure designs for flash flooding mitigation**. The research will describe the methodology framework of the design process that includes the explanation of the process required to run the simulations on open-source software *GRASS GIS*'s models *r.sim.water*; as well as the workflow between *GRASS GIS* and 3D modeling software such as *Rhinoceros 3D* and *Grasshopper*. The framework includes data collection, data processing, design interventions, simulation, analysis, and how to incorporate the feedback from the simulations to optimize the green infrastructure design. The project will explain the methodology framework through a case study in the city of LaPlace, Louisiana that will focus on testing hydrologic performance of a green infrastructure design. The results of this study will provide a framework that can be replicated for any location in the world, helping communities transition more easily to green infrastructure strategies and improving their resilience to climate change.

Table of Contents

Introduction	4
Literature Review	7
1. Simulations as tools for design decision making.....	7
1.1. Digital Model	7
1.1.1 Geospatial Data	8
1.2. Simulations	8
2. Framework Methodology	9
3. Hydrologic models in GRASS GIS.....	10
r.sim.water	10
4. Rhinoceros 3D Grasshopper’s Docofossor	11
Docofossor.....	12
5. Tutorials for Workflow Between GRASS GIS and Docofossor	12
Hydrology in GRASS GIS Tutorial.....	13
Grading Terrain with Grasshopper	16
Methods	18
1. Defining the framework.....	18
2. Case Study: Define Study Area	19
3. Applying the Methodology Framework.....	21
a. Data Acquisition.....	22
b. Data preparation on GRASS GIS.....	23
c. Modeling – Existing Conditions.....	28
d. Simulation.....	34
e. Design Intervention – Moving to Rhinoceros 3D Grasshopper Docofossor	36
f. Feedback.....	44
Results	49
Discussion and Conclusion	51
Bibliography	52

Introduction

Although climate change will affect the globe, it is no surprise that coastal zones and low-lying cities will be more affected by environmental impacts such as flooding events. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), climate change in the near term (next 20 years) will cause “[M]ore intense and frequent extreme rainfall and associated flooding in many regions including coastal and other low-lying cities, and increased proportion of and peak wind speeds of intense tropical cyclones.” The Fourth National Climate Assessment explains that “Many places are subject to more than one climate-related impact, such as extreme rainfall combined with coastal flooding... The compounding effects of these impacts result in increased risks to people, infrastructure, and interconnected economic sectors” (USGCRP, 2018). This is especially true for the Gulf States in the U.S. where according to the National Climate Assessment, the frequency and severity of extreme precipitation events are projected to continue increasing in the region (USGCRP, 2018). According to the report, the Southeast region of the U.S. has experienced an increase of 16% in observed 5-year maximum daily precipitation over the last decade (USGCRP, 2018). Louisiana is one of the Gulf States most affected by climate change. Climate change impacts like sea level rise, land loss, land subsidence, habitat degradation, extreme flooding, and changes in rainfall patterns pose significant risks to both coastal and inland communities.

As a response, the state government entrusted The Coastal Protection and Restoration Authority (CPRA) – “a single state entity to articulate a clear statement of priorities and to focus on development and implementation efforts to achieve comprehensive coastal protection for Louisiana” (*About CPRA*, n.d.)– to develop the 2023 Louisiana Comprehensive Master Plan for a Sustainable Coast. This plan was developed to “achieve comprehensive coastal restoration and risk reduction goals” for the Louisiana (*2023 Coastal Master Plan*, n.d.). Their findings for the highest-risk scenario suggest that the future of Louisiana's coast, without any climate risk mitigation efforts, will experience a 2.5 ft increase of sea level rise resulting in 3000 sq-mi of land loss in 50 years with storm surge flood depths increasing by an average of 30%, potentially reaching up to 21 ft in many coastal areas. CPRA's models project that economic damage associated with flood and intensified storms can total up to \$24.3 billion with at least 22,000 structures at risk of being damaged in coastal communities every year and thousands of people impacted (*2023 Coastal Master Plan*, n.d., pp. 36–49).

Since 2014, Louisiana has been the target of many flood-related disasters including the 2016 Louisiana flood that produced a damage toll of at least \$10.1 billion and 13 human casualties. During that event “rainfall totals across the region exceeded amounts that would be expected to occur once every 1,000 years (or a less than 0.1% annual probability of occurrence), causing the Amite and Comite Rivers to surge past their banks and resulting in some 50,000 homes across the region filling with more than 18

inches of water ”(USGCRP, 2018). It is expected that events like these will increase in frequency. The 2016 flood exemplifies how inland-urban area’s stormwater infrastructure can be affected by heavy rainfall events. Therefore, it is important that we begin to design our infrastructure with these climate hazard projections in mind.

To aid the aging and overwhelmed gray stormwater infrastructure, many communities in the country have started to implement green infrastructure systems. The Water Infrastructure Improvement Act, quoted by EPA, defines green infrastructure as "the range of measures that use plant or soil systems, permeable pavement or other permeable surfaces or substrates, stormwater harvest and reuse, or landscaping to store, infiltrate, or evapotranspire stormwater and reduce flows to sewer systems or to surface waters." Green infrastructure systems are designed to catch water where it falls and improve water quality, while also bringing other environmental, social and economic benefits such as improving biodiversity, habitat preservation, community gathering and recreation, economic revitalization, improving the sense of place and identity of a community, etc (US EPA, 2015). These strategies can be implemented at different scales from neighborhoods to complete watersheds, and these strategies range from bioswales, rain gardens, green roofs, permeable pavement, rainwater harvesting, urban canopy, constructed wetlands, to a network of all the strategies combined.

To help communities transition to green infrastructure, EPA has been developing digital models such as SWMM, VELMA, HSPF, and the National Stormwater Calculator. These tools allow communities to assess the performance of green infrastructure, and the cost associated with it before implementing them. For example, according to the EPA, “Kansas City, MO designed its \$10 million 100-acre Middle Blue River pilot on SWMM predictions and, based on the performance of this 100-acre pilot, it will design its \$2 billion, 20-year consent decree sewer upgrade ”(Matthew Hopton, Ph.D. et al., 2015). Since 2015, the Office of Research and Development has been making efforts to quantify the performance of green infrastructure strategies in many regions from water quality, to changes in runoff quantity. These regions include sites from Edison NJ, New York NY, State College PA, Clarksburg MD, Louisville KY, Cincinnati and Cleveland Oh, Detroit MI, Austin TX, Kansas City KS, and Denver CO (Matthew Hopton, Ph.D. et al., 2015, pp. 11–16).

The use of models can be very helpful and even critical for decision making to implement green infrastructure designs in communities. The models that EPA offers are often very sophisticated and targeted to engineers and scientists causing a breach between designers, such as landscape architects and architects, and STEM professionals. Therefore, in recent years, there has been an incentive to integrate hydrological models within geographical information systems (GIS) which are often used in design. The advantage of it is that the integration in the GIS world allows for better and more efficient data management, and is more user friendly. The use of simulations in GIS allows designers to test the feasibility of a green infrastructure design, optimize it, and quantify it. Also, it can promote the implementation of green infrastructure

technology since clients (i.e. communities) can be persuaded more efficiently to invest in sustainable strategies if they are shown with scientific quantifiable data that a particular design can work.

Thus, the **goal** of this research is to demonstrate **that hydrological simulations can be used as a design tool for designers such as landscape architects & architects to analyze the feasibility of green infrastructure designs for flash flooding mitigation.** To demonstrate the feasibility of a design through simulations, the research will describe the methodology framework of the design process that includes the explanation of the process required to run the simulations on open-source software GRASS GIS's model *r.sim.water*; as well as the workflow between *GRASS GIS* and 3D modeling software such as *Rhinoceros 3D* and *Grasshopper*. The framework includes data collection, data processing, design interventions, simulation, analysis, and how to incorporate the feedback from the simulations to optimize the green infrastructure design. The project will explain the methodology framework through a case study in LaPlace, Louisiana that will focus on testing hydrologic performance of a green infrastructure design. The results of this study will provide a framework that can be replicated for any location in the world, helping communities transition more easily to green infrastructure strategies and improving their resilience to climate change.

Literature Review

1. Simulations as tools for design decision making

Nowadays, the landscape architecture discipline intensively uses digital tools to conduct site analysis and model a design. However, this type of 3D modeling provides a static perspective or representation of a design that involves only conditions at a specific time (future, past or present) rather than the continuous conditions of different dynamics of an environment that occurs in the real world. Thus, there has been an incentive to research more in theory and in practice about design performance and develop the so-called 'digital twin' of a particular landscape that involves the combination of the static representation with the continuous change of conditions over time (Urech et al., 2022, p. 1).

Urech defines the concept of 'digital twin' as "[the description] of physical assets in time and at various frequencies for monitoring and planning cities" (p. 1) These models "integrate dynamic conditions of the environment to predict how designs will perform when they are implemented" (Urech et al., 2022, p. 1). The digital twin's main components include the digital model or the static representation, and the simulation or dynamic representation.

1.1. Digital Model

Digital Models offer a static representation of the landscape. Remote sensing technology, such as satellite and LIDAR (light detection and ranging), has been used to create **three-dimensional models** of cities with geospatial data. Remote sensing has been used extensively for mapping, visualization, generation of physical and digital models, environmental monitoring, and more (Urech et al., 2022, pp. 1–2). For instance, the United States Geological Survey (USGS) lists some examples of the common uses of remote sensing technology:

- The Climate R&D Program uses a range of remotely sensed data (including satellite imagery, historical photographs, and land-surface feature maps) to document landscape change and drivers, improve projections of future change, and identify impacts on infrastructure and society.
- Large forest fires can be mapped from space, allowing rangers to see a much larger area than from the ground.
- Tracking clouds to help predict the weather or watch erupting volcanoes, and observe dust storms.

- Tracking the growth of a city and changes in farmland or forests over several years or decades.
- Discovery and mapping of the rugged topography of the ocean floor (e.g., huge mountain ranges, deep canyons, and the “magnetic striping” on the ocean floor).
(*What Is Remote Sensing and What Is It Used for?* | U.S. Geological Survey, n.d.)
(*Remote Sensing* | U.S. Geological Survey, n.d.)

1.1.1 Geospatial Data

Different methods restructure the geospatial data from the LIDAR into more organized and usable data types such as Digital Surface Models and Digital Elevation Models. These data types are commonly used in geographical information softwares such as ArcGIS, GRASS GIS, and QGIS.

According to Hurkxkens, Digital Surface Models (DSM) are an “unordered point cloud” obtained from a topographic survey of the Earth’s surface through satellite, terrestrial and laser (LIDAR) scanning (Hurkxkens & Bernhard, 2019, pp. 222–223). This type of data includes all elevation or vertical points captured from the airborne devices, including trees, buildings, earth, etc.

In contrast, “a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is a representation of the bare ground (bare earth) topographic surface of the Earth excluding trees, buildings, and any other surface objects” and can be derived from LIDAR or other devices (*What Is a Digital Elevation Model (DEM)?* | U.S. Geological Survey, n.d.).

1.2. Simulations

According to Urech et al., dynamic systems or simulations allow “to predict how designs will perform under changing conditions such as the action of water, weather patterns, vegetation growth, anthropogenic activities” (Urech et al., 2022, p. 1). Consequently, there is a possibility for a constant interchange of information between the virtual and the natural environment, converting simulations into a powerful design tool. As Urech et al. states, “dynamic simulation supports the decision-making process of prospective scenarios using dynamic spatial models such as agent based modeling or cellular automata.” Also, it is a way to integrate scientific knowledge into the design making process and improve design feasibility (Urech et al., 2022, p. 1). In urban studies from various disciplines, different types of simulations have been implemented to research climate change in cities including “urban transformations, wind simulation with photogrammetric reconstruction, microclimate analysis, radiative transfer modeling,

shadow effect modeling, transpiration simulation” and hydrologic models (Urech et al., 2022, p. 1).

2. Framework Methodology

To implement simulations in the design process it is useful to develop a framework that will describe the workflow between different software. To clarify, let’s explain how design performance fits into a design development process: design performance can give you information about a design by “testing the shape..., and adapting [the] shape through digital prototyping” (Urech et al., 2022, p. 3). This allows for a framework that evaluates performance and provides feedback to designers for informing the design.

But to be able to run a simulation, many things must be prepared in advance to be able to fulfill the parameters required for each simulation. For example, Urech et. al, developed a 4 step framework that can run in cycles, beginning with the Iterative Modeling that includes building the geometry; the Static Evaluation that is basically processing of morphologic data of the geometry to feed parameters; Dynamic Evaluation which is running the simulation; and Change Detection where you get the feedback that can inform once again Iterative Modeling (3). Refer to Figure 1. This type of framework allows you to navigate in between the software and the different stages of design development and design assessment.

Figure 1 Overview of the methodological approach linking iterative point cloud modeling (a), static (b), and dynamic (c) evaluations, and change detection (d) in a loop (Urech et al., 2022, p. 3).

Very similarly, other authors such as Hofierka and Knutova, describes a framework of a SIMulated Water Erosion model (SIMWE) where workflows takes you from a static raster digital model on GRASS GIS (an open source geographical information systems software), to extracting and processing the data necessary to run the simulations called *r.sim.water*, and then running the simulation and getting the feedback that will inform the design (118-121).

3. Hydrologic models in GRASS GIS

r.sim.water

Currently, many researchers and professionals use HEC-RAS, ADCIRC, and others, which are standalone softwares for hydrological modeling. But in the past few years, there has been an incentive to integrate hydrological models within geographical information systems (GIS). The advantage of it is that the integration in the GIS world allows for better and more efficient data management. Also, open-source software such as GRASS GIS, allows for researchers to optimize the code if need be free of cost (Hofierka & Knutová, 2015, p. 118). Hofierka et. al, define GRASS GIS as “an open-source geospatial software consisting of modules dedicated to support solving various geospatial issues”(2015, p. 118).

Within GRASS GIS, a hydrological model called SIMulated Water Erosion or SIMWE has been developed to “simulat(e) the overland flow phenomenon that directly contributes to flooding” using the Monte Carlo simulation approach that describes the phenomenon with specific equations and approximations (Hofierka & Knutová, 2015, p. 119). According to Hofierka et. al, SIMWE, “a process based and spatially-distributed model” includes two different hydrological modules: *r.sim.water* which analyzes shallow overland flow, and *r.sediment* that focuses on sediment transport and deposition (2015, p. 119). For the purpose of this paper, we will focus on the hydrologic module of SIMWE, *r.sim.water*.

According to Hofierka et. al, *r.sim.water* simulates the **shallow water flow overland**. Although the module does not include waterways, this kind of hydrological analysis is particularly useful for **runoff estimations**. It is particularly useful for small basins (2015, p. 119). To do this, *r.sim.water* solves the bivariate shallow water flow equation known as St. Venant, resulting in the spatial distribution of water flow depth. The idea is to simulate how a particular site’s geophysical properties (land cover, topography, soil properties, etc) can be affected spatially over time in a particular short term rainfall event (Mitasova et al., 2004, p. 1480).

To run the hydrological simulation, preparation of data is needed. For *r.sim.water*, the input data necessary are raster digital elevation models, water flow gradients (first-order partial derivatives of elevation surface), rainfall excess rate, and Manning’s surface roughness. Depending on the project’s requirements, it is possible to add additional parameters to control and detail the simulation including number of walkers, iterations and diffusion (Mitasova et al., 2004, p. 1486).

Hofierka et al. describes some of the input data elements as:

- Digital Elevation Model: grid raster map with topographic elevation information.
- Water flow gradients: they are used to determine the velocity of water including its magnitude and direction in space. The partial derivatives must be calculated from the DEM and can be done within GRASS GIS with the *r.slope.aspect* or *v.surf.rst* module.

Figure 2 Flood depth rasters from *r.sim.water* (Hofierka & Knutová, 2015)

- Manning’s roughness coefficient: controls the velocity of water flow and is needed to calculate water flow gradients (2015, p. 121). These coefficients are numbers that are assigned to each type of land cover materials.
- Diffusion: “enables water flow to overcome elevation depressions or obstacles when water depths exceed a threshold water depth value” (2015, p. 120).
- Rainfall excess rate: “is defined as the difference between rainfall intensity and infiltration rate”(2015, p. 120).

After running *r.sim.water*, the simulation’s output are raster maps that represent constant water depth and discharge, and can be converted into a series of maps showing the evolution of inundation over time (Mitasova et al., 2004, p. 1486). (Hofierka & Knutová, 2015)

4. Rhinoceros 3D Grasshopper’s Docofossor

Rhinoceros 3D is a tridimensional modeling software commonly used by designers in architecture and landscape architecture professions. According to Rhinoceros 3D website, “Rhino can create, edit, analyze, document, render, animate, and translate NURBS curves, surfaces and solids, subdivision geometry (SubD), point clouds, and polygon meshes” (Robert McNeel, n.d.). Additionally, Rhinoceros contains a graphical algorithm editor used for parametric modeling called Grasshopper. As stated by Robert McNeel, “allows developers and designers to develop form-generation algorithms

without writing code” (Robert McNeel, n.d.). Moreover, within Grasshopper there are chances for specialized add-ons, or plugins, to maximize modeling.

Docofossor

Docofossor is a plugin for Grasshopper targeted to landscape architecture modeling. It was developed by Ilmar Hurkxkens and Mathias Bernhard from ETH Zurich. According to Hurkxkens et al., Docofossor “focuses on parametric transformations of a digital terrain model by point, path, area or surface on a digital terrain model (DTM). The collection of computational modeling components operate on a regular grid in 2.5D using distance functions” (Docofossor, 2019). This plugin allows for simple cut and fill operations for terrain modeling.

Docofossor aims to bridge the gap between raster type data—commonly used by GIS software— and NURBS to easily export and import surface models from Rhinoceros 3D. As stated by Hurkxkens et al., “Docofossor’s tools operate on a regular point grids and it is therefore easy to digitally exchange the data between various geographic information systems, simulation packages..., and 3D machine control systems...” (Hurkxkens & Bernhard, 2019, p. 224).

Figure 3 Cut and Fill Operations in Docofossor (Hurkxkens & Bernhard, 2019).

5. Tutorials for Workflow Between GRASS GIS and Docofossor

This study has generally followed the process for running hydrological simulations in GRASS GIS and parametric terrain modeling in Grasshopper’s Docofossor outlined by Harmon in his tutorials ‘Hydrology in GRASS GIS’ and ‘Grading Terrain in Grasshopper.’ Hydrology in GRASS GIS describes the process from processing the data and preparing it, to creating land cover maps with manning’s roughness coefficients, to running *r.sim.water* (Hydrology in GRASS GIS – Brendan Harmon, n.d.). On the other hand, on

Grading Terrain in Grasshopper, Harmon describes the step process on importing and modeling a digital elevation model (DEM) through parameters in Docofossor (*Grading Terrain in Grasshopper - YouTube*, n.d.).

Hydrology in GRASS GIS Tutorial

1. Preparing the Data

After importing the necessary datasets—typically a geoTIFF raster or point cloud of a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), along with four-band imagery—the first step is to begin processing within the GRASS GIS interface. Harmon suggests starting with a few essential commands:

- a. `g.region` – This command sets the computational region, essentially cropping your workspace to a defined rectangular area. Doing so ensures that all subsequent operations are limited to this region, which is especially helpful when working with large datasets.
- b. `r.neighbors` – Use this to smooth the raw DEM. It helps reduce noise in the elevation data, making it cleaner and more usable for analysis or visualization.
- c. `r.relie` – This generates a shaded relief map of the DEM, enhancing the terrain's visual appearance.
- d. `r.shade` – Finally, overlay the shaded relief onto the DEM to create a more visually informative representation of the terrain.

2. Shallow Water Flow

Harmon outlines two approaches for using the `r.sim.water` command in GRASS GIS. The first method is straightforward and relies on default parameters, while the second allows for customization using land cover data and Manning's roughness coefficients.

Before using either method, it's essential to calculate the partial derivatives **dx** and **dy** from the DEM raster using the `r.slope.aspect` command. According to the GRASS GIS manual:

“`r.slope.aspect` generates raster maps of slope, aspect, curvatures, and first- and second-order partial derivatives from a raster map of true elevation values” (Hofierka et al., 2009).

- **Method 1: Simple `r.sim.water`**

This method uses a basic setup with default environmental parameters. The required inputs for the command include:

- Elevation raster: DEM

- Rainfall rate: 150 mm/hr
 - Rainfall duration: 10 minutes
 - Number of walkers: 10,000
 - Output map names: Depth and discharge raster
- **Method 2: *r.sim.water* with NDVI-Based Land Cover**

As Harmon describes, vegetation indexes such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index can be used to classify land cover; including different classes of vegetation, dirt, or impervious surfaces. This is particularly useful to identify the water infiltration of the terrain. The command used is *i.vi*.

 - **Step 1:** Calculate NDVI

Use the *i.vi* command, which requires the red and near-infrared imagery bands as inputs:

```
i.vi input=red,infrared output=ndvi
```
 - **Step 2:** Recode NDVI to Manning's Coefficients

After generating the NDVI map, use *r.recode* to assign Manning's roughness values based on NDVI ranges. The syntax for the recode rules follows this format:

```
NDVI_min:NDVI_max:Manning_min:Manning_max
```
 - **Step 3:** Running *r.sim.water* as the first method but adding the recoded Manning's coefficient landcover map in the Manning's input option.

Harmon's recommendations on Manning's coefficients are:

NLCD Class	Landcover Category	Manning's n value
11	Open Water	0.001
21	Developed, Open Space	0.0404
22	Developed, Low Intensity	0.0678
23	Developed, Medium Intensity	0.0678
24	Developed, High Intensity	0.0404
31	Barren Land	0.0113
41	Deciduous Forest	0.36
42	Evergreen Forest	0.32
43	Mixed Forest	0.4
52	Shrub/Scrub	0.4
71	Grassland/Herbaceous	0.368
81	Pasture/Hay	0.325
82	Cultivated Crops	0.325
90	Woody Wetlands	0.086
95	Emergent Herbaceous Wetlands	0.1825

Figure 2: Mannings coefficients (*Hydrology in GRASS GIS – Brendan Harmon, n.d.*)

Grading Terrain with Grasshopper

This tutorial describes the process of modeling terrain in Grasshopper's Docofossor. The steps are as follows:

- **Step 1:** Importing data. In this case, it is a point cloud XYZ. It is important to identify a file path where the .xyz is stored on your pc. Since the point cloud is geo-localized to the exact coordinates on earth, it is useful to translate the coordinates to the local Rhino interface. Thus, it is recommended to use *Grid Shift* command.

Figure 4 Grasshopper script on importing terrain (Grading Terrain in Grasshopper - YouTube, n.d.).

- **Step 2:** Harmon describes two simple operations for modeling terrain using the Docofossor plugin. First, the *Cut and Fill In Path* that will cut and fill accordingly along a specified curve. The curve can also be parameterized through the interpolate command and a series of specified points. These points can be defined on the Rhinoceros graphical interface. The outcome will be a *docofossor distance field* which can be translated into a mesh with *df Grid Mesh* command.

Figure 5 Grading terrain operations that include the Cut and Fill path (Grading Terrain in Grasshopper - YouTube, n.d.).

- **Step 3:** The tutorial also explains how to make calculations on the cut and fill operations, and compare the new model with the existing DEM using the *Grid Compare* command.

Figure 6 Cut and Fill calculations with Grid Compare (Grading Terrain in Grasshopper - YouTube, n.d.).

Methods

1. Defining the framework

The proposed framework for the research was inspired by the framework methodology developed by Urech et al., that consists in a cycle of four consecutive steps where the last one will inform the first step and run the cycle as many times as needed (2022, p. 3). In this case, the four steps described by Urech et al. are: Iterative Modeling that includes building the geometry; the Static Evaluation that is processing of morphologic data of the geometry to feed parameters; Dynamic Evaluation which is running the simulation; and Change Detection where you get the feedback that can inform once again Iterative Modeling (3).

Moreover, the proposed framework consists of a series of steps of a simulation-integrated design process.

- **Step 1 Data Acquisition:** the necessary data to prepare the models for simulation is downloaded from different sources and different formats.
- **Step 2 Data Preparation:** the data, such as elevation and imagery, are processed in GRASS GIS.
- **Step 3 Modeling:** all the different kinds of data are compiled into one static model. This digital model offers a three-dimensional representation of a landscape, where site analysis can be performed. This model serves as the inputs for the next step.
- **Step 4 Simulation:** a simulation component integrated into GRASS GIS processes the data and simulates a phenomenon, in this case a flash flooding event. For *r.sim.water*, the outputs are a time series of raster maps showing the inundation event over time.
- **Step 5 Feedback:** the results are analyzed and inform design decisions. Depending on the results, the cycle can be repeated from the **Modeling** step to edit and optimize the design.

Figure 7 Overview of the methodological framework approach for simulations on the design process.

2. Case Study: Define Study Area

The case study area is within the boundary of the City of LaPlace in St. John the Baptist Parish, Louisiana. This city is surrounded by three bodies of water: the wetlands of Lake Maurepas to the north, the wetlands of Lake Pontchartrain towards the east, and the Mississippi River to the south.

The case study's green infrastructure design was **inspired** by a previous project done by the author during an internship in 2023 at the LSU Coastal Ecosystem Design Studio (Jimenez, 2023).

Furthermore, the case study's proposed green infrastructure design attempts to aid the city's aging grey infrastructure mitigating flash flooding. The design provides a variety of other ecosystem services including connectivity, recreation, improved water quality, habitat and biodiversity. The study area was defined by the canal running parallel to Highway 51 to the west where a blueway intervention was proposed with the main goal of slowing down water. The study area encompasses the Thomas A Daley Memorial Park north of Highway 61, and the neighborhoods adjacent to the canal south of Interstate-10 where bioswales were proposed to connect the hydrologic system to the blueway. An intervention of a stormwater park for water storage was proposed at Thomas A Daley Memorial Park which included detention ponds and rain gardens.

Figure 8 Proposed green infrastructure design. Consists of a meandering naturalized canal or blueway with a primary goal of slowing down water. Other strategies include detention ponds, bioswales, and rain gardens.

LaPlace, Louisiana

Severely affected by flooding

Figure 9 Study area with a flood hazards map (left). Inspiration for green infrastructure design of a meandering blueway (right) (Jimenez, 2023).

3. Applying the Methodology Framework

Figure 9, 10, and 11 shows an overview of the process to run simulations on GRASS GIS and model the proposed green infrastructure design with parametric design on Rhino 3D with Grasshopper's Docofossor plugin.

Figure 10 Methodology framework with GRASS GIS commands. This shows the different GRASS GIS commands used and in which stage of the process they belong.

Shallow Water Simulation with r.sim.water Flowchart

Figure 11 Flowchart of Shallow Water Simulation with r.sim.water. This shows the flow of data from input raw data to running r.sim.water simulation and obtaining final outputs of depth and discharge.

Figure 12 Flowchart of the process of grading in Docofossor within Rhino 3D. The flowcharts shows the process from input of the point clouds and curves, to output of the final terrain, and exporting it to a compatible XYZ point cloud.

a. Data Acquisition

In this step, the required data for running the simulation models is collected from various sources and in different formats.

To use the *r.sim.water* module in GRASS GIS, specific data types and formats are necessary. The simulation can be run at almost any scale, but its speed is primarily limited by computing power and processing time. Larger areas will take longer to simulate.

As previously mentioned, *r.sim.water* requires the following input data: **raster-based digital elevation models (DEMs)**, **water flow gradients** (first-order partial derivatives of the elevation surface), **rainfall excess rates**, and **Manning’s roughness coefficients** (on a landcover map or as a constant number). Additional parameters—such as the number of walkers, iterations, and diffusion settings—can be included to refine the simulation, depending on project needs (Mitasova et al., 2004, p. 1486).

On the table below, the data used for the project is listed as follows:

Data Type	File Type	Website	Name	Projection	Collection Author
Raster Elevation Data	Point Cloud and geoTIFF	NOAA Digital Access Viewer	la2017_up_delta_pln_dem_J1086242	NAD83(2011) / Louisiana South	2017 USGS Lidar: Upper Delta Plain U.S. Geological Survey
Imagery 8-bit	geoTIFF	NOAA Digital Access Viewer	x021_4BandImage ry_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.1 x021_4BandImage ry_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.2 x021_4BandImage ry_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.3 x021_4BandImage ry_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.4	NAD83(2011) / Louisiana South	2021 USDA NAIP 4-Band 8 bit imagery, Louisiana. U.S. Department of Agriculture
Manning's coefficient tables	txt	Hydrology in GRASS GIS	Manning's roughness coefficient	n/a	Brendan Harmon

b. Data preparation on GRASS GIS

Before running any simulation, the acquired raw data must be prepared and/or processed.

1. Import the data into GRASS GIS using *r.import*

This command only requires the file path where the data is located on your computer, the resampling method if it is DEM, and the name of the output. This command was used for both the DEM and the imagery.

Importing DEM

```

` ``r.import resample=bicubic
input=C:\Users\lab\Documents\grassdata\laplace_data\la2017_
up_delta_pln_dem_Job1086242\la2017_up_delta_pln_dem_J108624
2.tif output=la2017_up_delta_pln_dem_J1086242` ``

```

2. Rescaling the DEM with *r.mapcalc*

GRASS GIS works more efficiently in meters. In this case, the data had the elevation measured in feet. Thus, we rescale it to meters with map algebra *r.mapcalc* and assign the output name 'elevation.'

```
```\n\nr.mapcalc expression="elevation =\n1a2017_up_delta_pln_dem_J1086242@PERMANENT * 0.3048"\n```\n
```

## 3. Visualize the data with *r.relief* and *r.shade*

There are a couple of useful commands in GRASS GIS to better visualize the elevation data, including *r.relief* and *r.shade*. *R.relief* creates a shaded relief map, which uses shading and color to simulate a three-dimensional appearance of the terrain. On the other hand, *r.shade* will allow to drape a color raster over the relief map.

*R.relief* – the only required input is the elevation or DEM.

```
```\nr.relief input=elevation@PERMANENT output=shaded_elevation\n```\n
```


Figure 13 Shaded relief of the existing terrain

4. Imagery Processing

Oftentimes, the imagery data may come in quadrants that have to be grouped to compose a raster that covers your whole study area. This process is called mosaic. In addition, the imagery must be mosaiced into the different bands. Look for the metadata to understand the different bands from the imagery.

We begin by classifying the files into the different bands with *g.list*, and then mosaic with *r.patch*. In the case of *g.list*, the type of list (raster), the pattern (in this case, every file that belongs to each band has an ending), and the separator (comma) are needed. *R.patch* will take each previously defined list and join them together into one single raster with a specified output name.

Lastly, for better visualization you can create a composite of all the bands to make a true color imagery raster *r.composite*.

Red Band

```
...  
g.list type=raster pattern=*.1 separator=comma  
...  
...  
r.patch  
input=x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_001.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_002.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_000.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_001.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_002.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_000.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_001.1,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_002.1 output=imagery_1  
...
```

Green Band

```
...  
g.list type=raster pattern=*.2 separator=comma  
...  
...
```

```
r.patch
input=x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.2,x021_4BandIm
agery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_001.2,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1
086246_000_002.2,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_000.2,x
021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_001.2,x021_4BandImagery_L
ouisiana_J1086246_001_002.2,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_
002_000.2,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_001.2,x021_4Ba
ndImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_002.2 output=imagery_2
...
```

Blue Band

```
...
g.list type=raster pattern=*.3 separator=comma
...
...
r.patch
input=x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.3,x021_4BandIm
agery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_001.3,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1
086246_000_002.3,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_000.3,x
021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_001.3,x021_4BandImagery_L
ouisiana_J1086246_001_002.3,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_
002_000.3,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_001.3,x021_4Ba
ndImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_002.3 output=imagery_3
...
```

Near-Infrared Band

```
...
g.list type=raster pattern=*.4 separator=comma
...
...
r.patch
input=x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_000.4,x021_4BandIm
agery_Louisiana_J1086246_000_001.4,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1
086246_000_002.4,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_000.4,x
021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_001_001.4,x021_4BandImagery_L
ouisiana_J1086246_001_002.4,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_
```

```
002_000.4,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_001.4,x021_4BandImagery_Louisiana_J1086246_002_002.4 output=imagery_4  
```
```

```
```r.slope.aspect --overwrite  
elevation=proposedelevationoptimized@PERMANENT dx=dxpo dy=dypo  
```
```

### True Color Composite

```
````  
r.composite red=imagery_1 green=imagery_2 blue=imagery_3  
output=true_color  
````
```



Figure 14 Red band (top left), green band (top right), blue band (bottom left), near-infrared band (bottom right).



Figure 15 True color image combining all the bands from the imagery with r.composite.

### c. Modeling – Existing Conditions

The previously processed data is compiled into one static model that will be used as input parameters for the simulation. This digital model offers a static representation of a landscape, and it is very useful to analyze the existing conditions of the site. To create this comprehensive model of the terrain, the data must be converted and layered together with different commands. For instance, it is in this phase that we are using the imagery data to create land cover maps.

#### 1. Calculating Vegetation Indices with *i.vi* To Create Land Cover Maps

Land cover maps will allow us to identify where run off is being absorbed and slowed down on the terrain. For instance, vegetation can absorb or percolate water and slow it down more than an impervious surface like concrete or asphalt would. To create these maps, vegetation indexes such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) can be useful. The required input for any of the vegetation indexes in the command *i.vi* are the imagery with the different bands we mosaiced in the previous step.

Calculate Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

\*\*\*

```
i.vi output=ndvi vname=ndvi red=imagery_1 nir=imagery_4
green=imagery_2 blue=imagery_3
```

\*\*\*

Calculate Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)

\*\*\*

```
i.vi output=ndwi vname=ndwi red=imagery_1 nir=imagery_4
green=imagery_2 blue=imagery_3
```

\*\*\*

Calculate Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)

\*\*\*

```
i.vi --overwrite output=evi vname=evi red=imagery_1
nir=imagery_4 green=imagery_2 blue=imagery_3
```



Figure 16 NDVI land cover map.



Figure 17 NDWI map



Figure 18 EVI map

## 2. Re-coding NDVI Landcover Map with Mannings Roughness Coefficient

While the NDVI map may appear correct visually, the next step is to recode the NDVI value ranges into fixed numbers that represent different friction coefficients. By assigning Manning's roughness coefficients, we can estimate the terrain's water infiltration rate. To do this, we use the *r.recode* command, defining rules that convert NDVI values into corresponding Manning's roughness values.

The syntax for the recode rules follows this format:

```
NDVI_min:NDVI_max:Manning_min:Manning_max
```

Formula for recode:

```
-0.9:-0.7:0.001:0.001
-0.1:0:0.0678:0.0678
0.01:0.09:0.0113:0.0113
0.2:0.5:0.4:0.4
0.1:0.19:0.368:0.368
```

The following values for Manning's coefficient were used:

Water- 0.001

Concrete- 0.0678

Bare Ground - 0.0113

Mixed Forest - 0.4

Grass - 0.368

```
```\n
```

```
r.recode -a --overwrite input=ndvi@PERMANENT output=ndvi_mannings  
rules=C:\\Users\\lab\\Documents\\grassdata\\laplace\\PERMANENT\\.tmp\\unk  
nown\\17116.0
```

```
```\n
```



Figure 19 Recoded NDVI landcover map with Manning's roughness coefficients.

### 3. Calculating Partial Derivatives of the DEM with *r.slope.aspect*

Another required input for running *r.sim.water* are the partial derivatives *dx* and *dy*. To run *r.slope.aspect*, we only need the rescaled DEM and the output maps' names.

```

```

```
r.slope.aspect --overwrite elevation=elevation@PERMANENT dx=dx
dy=dy
```

```

```



Figure 20 Partial derivatives dx (top) and dy (bottom).

## d. Simulation

This step integrates dynamic conditions with the static model. This combination of the static model and the dynamic model is what Urech et al. defines as ‘digital twin,’ which “integrate[s] dynamic conditions of the environment to predict how designs will perform when they are implemented” (Urech et al., 2022, p. 1). In the case of hydrologic simulations like *r.sim.water*, it simulates the phenomenon of a flash flooding event over time. The simulation’s output are raster maps that represent constant water depth and discharge, and can be converted into a series of maps showing the evolution of inundation over time (Mitasova et al., 2004, p. 1486). This step is crucial to understand the existing hydrology of the site, and the altered proposed hydrology.

The parameters required to run *r.sim.water* are:

- a. Digital Elevation Model DEM raster
- b. Partial derivatives outputs calculated from the DEM with the *r.slope.aspect*
- c. Manning’s roughness coefficient.
  1. Raster of land cover map re-coded with Mannings’ roughness coefficients values; or
  2. Constant value
- d. Number of walkers
- e. Duration of the rainfall event
- f. Rainfall event intensity
- g. Names for the outputs for water depth and discharge maps
- h. Optionally: time-series outputs with number of iterations and step count

### Running shallow water hydrological simulation with *r.sim.water*

```
...
r.sim.water -t --overwrite elevation=elevation@PERMANENT dx=dx
dy=dy rain_value=150 man=ndvi_mannings@PERMANENT depth=depth_zoom
discharge=discharge_zoom nwalkers=10000 niterations=30
output_step=10
...
```



Figure 21 Simulation of water depth during a 150 mm/hr storm with time stamps every 10 minutes. The series shows the inundation on the existing terrain over time.

## e. Design Intervention – Moving to Rhinoceros 3D Grasshopper’s Docofossor

### 1. Export from GRASS GIS with *r.out.gdal*

To import the DEM into Docofossor, it is essential to first export the dataset from GRASS GIS as a point cloud ASCII Grid format. This format resolves a known mirroring issue within Docofossor. The export is performed using the *r.out.gdal* command, with the output format specified as *AAIGrid* and the file path defined with a *.asc* extension.

Export to ASCII grid AAI Grid

```
``r.out.gdal --overwrite input=elevation@PERMANENT
output=C:\Users\lab\Documents\grassdata\laplaceelevati
ondgdal.asc format=AAIGrid
``
```

### 2. Import into Rhinoceros Grasshopper with Docofossor Plugin

Once Rhinoceros 3D and Grasshopper are launched, the ASCII Grid is imported via the Docofossor plugin using the *Import ASC* component. Within this component, both the grid resolution and the file path to the *.asc* file must be specified.

Since the point cloud is geo-localized to the exact coordinates on earth, it is useful to translate the coordinates to the local Rhino interface. Thus, the *Import ASC* component output *df* is connected to the *Grid Shift* command.

For better visualization of the Digital Elevation Model, the docofossor list (*df*) output from the *Grid Shift* is connected to a *Grid Mesh* and *Custom Preview* components with a specified color. However, it is important to know that the *distance field (df)* created by the *Grid Shift* is the one that will be used to represent the existing conditions DEM. Thus, it is recommended to store it in its own data component and name it 'Existing DF.'



Figure 22 Importing existing terrain as an AAI point cloud.

### 3. Grading with Docofossor

With Docofossor, it is possible to do simple operations for modeling terrain. First, the *Cut and Fill In Path* that will cut and fill accordingly along a specified curve. The curve can also be parameterized through the interpolate command and a series of specified points. These points can be defined on the Rhinoceros graphical interface. This command is useful to create bioswales or canals.

*Cut and Fill in Surface* works similarly to the path, but with a specified closed curve. The command takes the points along the curve to fit it into the landscape with a specified slope. This command can be used to create ponds, lakes, depressions, and rain gardens.

Although there are other commands, the absolute Cut and Fill operations were mainly used for this study. However, for all commands, the outcome will be a *distance field* which can be translated into a mesh with *Grid Mesh* command.

It is important to note that the sequence of operations directly affects the resulting terrain grading or surface model. As a general guideline, *Fill* operations should be executed prior to *Cut* operations. These processes are sequentially linked, with the output of each operation serving as the input for the subsequent one.

#### a. Fill existing swale

A curve drawn on the Rhinoceros graphical interface is brought into Grasshopper with a *curve* command. This one is moved to a specified height in meters. This transformed curve is the input for the *Fill in Path* command, which needs parameters of width of the path, depth, inner and

outer slope degree, and the maximum distance that it can span. The result is then an input for the next operation.



Figure 23 Fill in Path operation in Docofossor.

## b. Cut a bioswale with a non-uniform slope

To model more complex swales, the base curve must first be parameterized. This process begins by extracting the control points from the curve. These points are then modified along the Z-axis using the *Move* component to shape the swale's vertical profile.

To define the vertical displacement, a *Graph Mapper* is used to control the Z-values, effectively allowing a sectional visualization of the swale's profile. For this bioswale, the profile starts at a lower elevation, rises to a peak, and then slopes downward—creating a hill-like form.

To achieve this shape, the control points are first organized into a list. Their numerical values are then remapped to a normalized domain (0 to 1), which serves as the input range for the *Graph Mapper*. The *Graph Mapper* applies a mathematical function—in this case, a Bezier curve—to redistribute the values along the Z-axis. To better interpret the adjusted heights, it can be helpful to use a *Note* component connected to the *Graph Mapper* output.

Once the desired profile is defined, the values are remapped again to match the actual elevation range in meters. These final values are then used in the *Move* component to generate the adjusted curve, which becomes the input for the *Cut and Fill Path* operation.

The *Cut and Fill Path* component requires the following inputs: the previous *df*, the parameterized base curve, the path width, inner and outer slope values, and the maximum allowable span distance.

This study includes two examples demonstrating bioswales with non-uniform slopes.



Figure 24 Two alternatives of parametrizing a bioswale with non-uniform slopes

### c. Cutting bioswale with a uniform slope

Creating a bioswale with a uniform slope is a straightforward process. It begins by extracting the control points from the base curve. These points are then adjusted along the Z-axis using the *Move* component to define the swale's vertical gradient.

To control the Z-axis displacement, the control points are first compiled into a list. A *Series* component is then used to generate a sequence of values based on the number of control points, specifying the start value and step increment to establish the slope. This series is then remapped to a target elevation range, which defines the vertical profile of the swale. The remapped values are connected to the Z input of the *Move* component, resulting in a uniformly sloped curve. This modified curve is then used as an input for the *Cut and Fill Path* component.



Figure 25 Blueway that slopes uniformly Cut in Path

#### d. Creating a pond with Cut and Fill Surface

This operation generates either a depression or an extrusion based on a closed polygonal curve. The polygon can be modeled directly within the Rhinoceros interface and adjusted vertically along the Z-axis using a standard *Move* command. The resulting curve serves as one of the inputs for the *Cut and Fill in Surface* component, which also requires the specification of a slope (in degrees) and a maximum span distance.



Figure 26 Pond (top) and rain garden (bottom) with Cut & Fill In Surface.

#### 4. Calculations

To calculate the volumetric difference from the proposed design and the existing conditions DEM, a *Grid Compare* command can be used.



Figure 27 Calculation of the difference between existing terrain vs proposed terrain.

#### 5. Visualization of proposed design

To visualize, the final terrain is converted to a mesh. It can be exaggerated with a *Scale NU* for better visualization.



Figure 28 Visualization of final terrain with Custom Preview.

#### 6. Creating Contours

Creating contours with Grasshopper is very simple; only input the mesh from the final terrain into the *Contours* command and define the contour interval. The generated contours can be 'baked' or translated into the Rhinoceros 3D graphical interface.



Figure 29 Creating contours from proposed terrain.

## 7. Exporting as an XYZ Point Cloud to GRASS GIS

The final step involves exporting the proposed design as geospatial data for simulation in GRASS GIS. Before export, the model must be reprojected to real-world coordinates using the *Grid Global* component.

It is important to note that when exporting from Docofossor, the data must be saved in the XYZ point cloud format; other formats will not be compatible with GRASS GIS. To export, specify a file name and activate the Boolean toggle to generate the .xyz point cloud file.



Figure 30 Exporting as an XYZ point cloud.

## f. Feedback

The simulation results offer valuable insights into the site's hydrology. The water depth raster highlights areas where water tends to accumulate and form ponds, while the discharge raster illustrates the flow velocity of water across the terrain during storm events.

Another recommendation to understand further the hydrology of the site is to use the command *r.watershed* to delineate drainage basins and identify natural waterways or streams.

In this case study, the design objective was to retain and slow down water movement as much as possible, reducing the burden on the aging municipal drainage system downstream in the watershed.

To quantify the results of the hydrologic simulations for both the existing terrain and the proposed design, the *r.univar* tool in GRASS GIS can be used. According to the GRASS GIS manual, *r.univar* “calculates univariate statistics from the non-null cells of a raster map,” including “metrics such as the number of cells, minimum and maximum values, range, mean, variance, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and sum (r.univar - GRASS GIS Manual, n.d.).” These statistics help evaluate the hydrologic performance of a design based on raster data.

For this study, comparisons between the existing terrain and the proposed design were made to assess depth and discharge. For calculating depth, the process involves subtracting the **sum** of the existing conditions simulated depth raster from the **sum** of the proposed design. This difference indicates the total volume of runoff captured in the proposed design at a specific timeframe in the simulation. Since the units are in cubic meters, each raster cell represents one cubic meter of water. The percentage increase in depth was then calculated based on this volume difference.

The same method was applied to evaluate changes in discharge, but instead of the sum, we evaluate the **mean** and the **maximum**. These represent the average water velocity and the maximum velocity of the water during a specific time in the storm.

The quantitative data and analysis from the simulation statistics are then used to optimize the design.

Below are some samples of the data generated from running *r.univar* on the *r.sim.water* outputs discharge and depth rasters:

## DEPTH

r.univar map=selection\_depth\_zoom\_30@PERMANENT

total null and non-null cells: 3633120

total null cells: 3452166

Of the non-null cells:

-----

n: 180954

minimum: 0.000257539

maximum: 0.963101

range: 0.962843

mean: 0.0665003

mean of absolute values: 0.0665003

standard deviation: 0.0842621

variance: 0.00710011

variation coefficient: 126.709 %

**sum: 12033.4928896952**

r.univar map=selection\_depth\_optimized\_30@PERMANENT

total null and non-null cells: 3633120

total null cells: 3452208

Of the non-null cells:

-----

n: 180912

minimum: 0.000261458

maximum: 0.799374

range: 0.799113

mean: 0.0836507

mean of absolute values: 0.0836507

standard deviation: 0.0923213

variance: 0.00852322

variation coefficient: 110.365 %

**sum: 15133.4097336885**

depth at 30 min in volume m3

(proposed) 15133.4097336885 - (existing) 12033.4928896952=

3,099.9168439933 m3

25% of added volume

Depth at 10 min  
Proposed - Existing  
110602.164831101 - 110321.8724589 = 280.292372201 0.25%

Depth at 20 min  
163611.836246297 - 163233.26889341= 378.567352887 0.23%

Depth at 30 min  
207869.716640781 - 207303.239291211= 566.47734957 0.27%

## DISCHARGE

r.univar --overwrite map=discharge\_zoom.10@PERMANENT

total null and non-null cells: 3633120

total null cells: 0

Of the non-null cells:

-----

n: 3633120

minimum: -1.38404e-005

**maximum: 88.8448**

range: 88.8448

**mean: 0.0127228**

mean of absolute values: 0.0127229

standard deviation: 0.182821

variance: 0.0334237

variation coefficient: 1436.96 %

sum: 46223.4652822034

r.univar --overwrite map=discharge\_optimized.10@PERMANENT

total null and non-null cells: 3633120

total null cells: 7680

Of the non-null cells:

-----

n: 3625440

minimum: -1.44258e-005

**maximum: 46.1592**

range: 46.1592

**mean: 0.0121141**

mean of absolute values: 0.0121141

standard deviation: 0.143198

variance: 0.0205055

variation coefficient: 1182.08 %

sum: 43918.8204293089

r.univar --overwrite map=discharge\_optimized.20@PERMANENT  
total null and non-null cells: 3633120  
total null cells: 7680  
Of the non-null cells:  
-----  
n: 3625440  
minimum: -2.36361e-005  
**maximum: 51.7287**  
range: 51.7287  
**mean: 0.0261037**  
mean of absolute values: 0.0261039  
standard deviation: 0.25396  
variance: 0.0644955  
variation coefficient: 972.886 %  
sum: 94637.5296853784

r.univar --overwrite map=discharge\_zoom.20@PERMANENT  
total null and non-null cells: 3633120  
total null cells: 0  
Of the non-null cells:  
-----  
n: 3633120  
minimum: -2.38973e-005  
**maximum: 152.948**  
range: 152.948  
**mean: 0.0275547**  
mean of absolute values: 0.0275548  
standard deviation: 0.35228  
variance: 0.124101  
variation coefficient: 1278.48 %  
sum: 100109.510475428

r.univar --overwrite map=discharge\_optimized.30@PERMANENT  
total null and non-null cells: 3633120  
total null cells: 7680  
Of the non-null cells:  
-----  
n: 3625440  
minimum: -4.5834e-005  
**maximum: 52.9858**  
range: 52.9859  
**mean: 0.0416152**  
mean of absolute values: 0.0416154  
standard deviation: 0.371954

variance: 0.13835  
variation coefficient: 893.794 %  
sum: 150873.480537982

r.univar --overwrite map=discharge\_zoom.30@PERMANENT

total null and non-null cells: 3633120

total null cells: 0

Of the non-null cells:

-----

n: 3633120

minimum: -4.70466e-005

**maximum: 212.245**

range: 212.245

**mean: 0.0441085**

mean of absolute values: 0.0441087

standard deviation: 0.53084

variance: 0.281791

variation coefficient: 1203.48 %

sum: 160251.632979804

Calculations of discharge:

10 minutes

$0.0121141$  (proposed) -  $0.0127229$ (existing) =  $-0.0006088$  4.7%

maximums  $88.8448 - 46.1592 = 42.6856$  43%

In the first 10 min, it is 4.7% slower in average, but on maximums is the same speed.

In the maximum speed, the proposed design is slower by 43%

20 minutes

Proposed - Existing

$0.0261037 - 0.0275547 = -0.001451$  5.6%

maximums  $51.7287 - 152.948 = -101.2193$  66%

When it reaches the 20 min, the discharge in average is 5.6% slower and 42% slower in the maximum speed

30 min

Proposed - existing

$0.0416152 - 0.0441085 = -0.0024933$  5%

max  $52.9859 - 212.245 = -159.2591$  -75%

With a 30 min storm, the discharge keeps decreasing on an average of 5%. And the maximum speed decreases by 75%

## Results

The results from the *r.sim.water* simulation indicate that the proposed green infrastructure design—including a blueway, stormwater park with bioswales, detention ponds, and rain gardens—**effectively achieve its primary goal: slowing water velocity or discharge**. This helps alleviate stress on the city’s aging and often-overflowing drainage system, thereby reducing flood risks.

Figure 32 presents water depth raster maps comparing the existing terrain with the proposed design. Visually, the intervention areas effectively capture runoff over time. Supporting this observation, *r.univar* analysis shows the proposed design adds **3,099 m<sup>3</sup>** of water storage capacity to the site—a **25% increase**.

The discharge results are particularly noteworthy. As shown in Figure 33:

- At 10 minutes into the storm, the **maximum velocity** drops **43%**, from 89 m<sup>3</sup>/s (existing) to 46 m<sup>3</sup>/s (proposed).
- At 20 minutes, the reduction is **42%**, from 153 m<sup>3</sup>/s to 52 m<sup>3</sup>/s.
- At 30 minutes, the velocity decreases **75%**, from 212 m<sup>3</sup>/s to 53 m<sup>3</sup>/s.

While the mean velocity across the site changes only slightly, the **substantial reduction in peak velocity** indicates that high-speed water flow—previously contributing to downstream flooding—has been significantly curbed, thereby mitigating flood hazards.



Figure 31 Existing Digital Elevation Model and Proposed Digital Elevation Model.

# Results

Water Depth m- 150 mm/hr big storm



Figure 32 Water depth results from a 150 mm/hr storm. These series of maps shows the inundation over 30 minutes. The key thing here is that the proposed design (bottom row) is storing water.

# Results

Discharge m<sup>3</sup>/s- 150 mm/hr big storm



Figure 33 Simulated discharge maps on a 150 mm/hr storm. From the 10 minutes, the difference in peak elevation is substantial from the existing conditions to the proposed design. Overall, the proposed design is significantly slower.

## Discussion and Conclusions

This study demonstrates that green infrastructure interventions—such as naturalized meandering canals (blueways)—can significantly slow water flow, supporting existing urban drainage systems and reducing flood hazards. It also shows that strategies like rain gardens and detention ponds can store substantial volumes of water. These findings confirm that green infrastructure offers a sustainable alternative for urban stormwater management, while also providing a wide range of environmental, social, and economic benefits. These include improved mental health, recreation opportunities, connectivity, walkability, enhanced sense of place and identity, increased biodiversity and habitat quality, improved water quality, environmental conservation, and economic revitalization.

The proposed methodology demonstrated that hydrological simulations can be used as a design tool for designers—landscape architects, urban designers and planners, architects, etc—to assess the feasibility of a green infrastructure design for flash flooding mitigation. By analyzing the effectiveness of green infrastructure in mitigating flash flooding, designers can validate and optimize their designs with evidence-based confidence before construction begins. This empowers communities to adopt green infrastructure more readily, knowing from the outset that the approach is grounded in scientifically quantifiable results. Moreover, this data can help secure funding by demonstrating that the proposed solutions are both feasible and effective.

The integration of GRASS GIS with Rhinoceros 3D further strengthens this methodology by showcasing software interoperability and efficient data management, something not always available on other platforms. Both programs are widely used in the design field and offer intuitive, visual interfaces, making it easier to integrate simulations directly into the design process and for designers to adopt the workflow.

Ultimately, this study advocates for the widespread adoption of green infrastructure to enhance community resilience, especially in areas increasingly affected by climate change-related flooding. Improving the design process for this sustainable technology supports its broader implementation. The proposed methodology is adaptable and can be replicated globally, limited only by the availability of necessary data and access to the required software.

Future research is recommended to explore advancements in computational design and develop strategies to bridge the gap between hydrological simulations and 3D modeling. Furthermore, exploring cross-disciplinary approaches to computational design may enhance collaboration and support the broader implementation of green infrastructure technologies.

## Bibliography

- 2023 Coastal Master Plan*. (n.d.). Coastal Protection And Restoration Authority. Retrieved December 8, 2023, from <https://coastal.la.gov/our-plan/2023-coastal-master-plan/>
- About CPRA*. (n.d.). Coastal Protection And Restoration Authority. Retrieved May 10, 2024, from <https://coastal.la.gov/about/>
- Docofossor*. (2019, June 6). [Text]. Food4Rhino. <https://www.food4rhino.com/en/app/docofossor>
- Grading terrain in Grasshopper—YouTube*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 7, 2025, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Eih1g-tjFpc>
- Hofierka, J., & Knutová, M. (2015). Simulating spatial aspects of a flash flood using the Monte Carlomethod and GRASS GIS: A case study of the Malá Svinka Basin(Slovakia). *Open Geosciences*, 7(1), 20150013. <https://doi.org/10.1515/geo-2015-0013>
- Hofierka, J., Mitášová, H., & Neteler, M. (2009). Chapter 17 Geomorphometry in GRASS GIS. In *Developments in Soil Science* (Vol. 33, pp. 387–410). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481\(08\)00017-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481(08)00017-2)
- Hurkxkens, I., & Bernhard, M. (2019). *Computational Terrain Modeling with Distance Functions for Large Scale Landscape Design*. Wichmann Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.14627/537663024>
- Hydrology in GRASS GIS – Brendan Harmon*. (n.d.). Retrieved November 2, 2023, from <https://baharmon.github.io/hydrology-in-grass>
- Jimenez, Clara. (2023) LaPlace Green Infrastructure Network. Louisiana State University Coastal Ecosystem Design Studio. <https://www.lsu.edu/ceds/research/index.php>.
- Matthew Hopton, Ph.D., Michelle Simon, Ph.D., P.E., Michael Borst, Ahjond Garmestani, Ph.D., J.D., Scott Jacobs, Dennis Lye, Ph.D., Thomas O'Connor, P.E., & William Shuster, Ph.D. (2015). Green Infrastructure for Stormwater Control: Gauging Its Effectiveness with Community Partners. *U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Office of Research and*

*Development National Risk Management Research Laboratory Water Supply and Water Resources Division.*

Mitasova, H., Thaxton, C., Hofierka, J., McLaughlin, R., Moore, A., & Mitas, L. (2004). Path sampling method for modeling overland water flow, sediment transport, and short term terrain evolution in Open Source GIS. In *Developments in Water Science* (Vol. 55, pp. 1479–1490). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-5648\(04\)80159-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-5648(04)80159-X)

*Remote Sensing* | U.S. Geological Survey. (n.d.). Retrieved May 10, 2024, from <https://www.usgs.gov/programs/climate-research-and-development-program/science/science-topics/remote-sensing>

Robert McNeel, A. (n.d.). *Features*. Wwww.Rhino3d.Com. Retrieved April 8, 2024, from <https://www.rhino3d.com/features/>

*r.univar—GRASS GIS manual*. (n.d.). Retrieved May 7, 2025, from <https://grass.osgeo.org/grass-stable/manuals/r.univar.html>

Urech, P. R. W., Mughal, M. O., & Bartesaghi-Koc, C. (2022). A simulation-based design framework to iteratively analyze and shape urban landscapes using point cloud modeling. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 91, 101731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2021.101731>

US EPA, O. (2015, September 30). *What is Green Infrastructure?* [Overviews and Factsheets]. <https://www.epa.gov/green-infrastructure/what-green-infrastructure>

USGCRP. (2018). *Fourth National Climate Assessment* (pp. 1–470). U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC. <https://nca2018.globalchange.gov><https://nca2018.globalchange.gov/chapter/19>

*What is a digital elevation model (DEM)?* | U.S. Geological Survey. (n.d.). Retrieved April 8, 2024, from <https://www.usgs.gov/faqs/what-digital-elevation-model-dem>

*What is remote sensing and what is it used for?* | U.S. Geological Survey. (n.d.). Retrieved May 10, 2024, from <https://www.usgs.gov/faqs/what-remote-sensing-and-what-it-used>